

IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

ConcePTION

WP5 – Dissemination and education for HCPs, pregnant and breastfeeding women and general public

D5.13 Annual report on external communications for impact assessment January - December 2022

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Document History

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Abstract

The main aim of WP5 is to improve the value, quality and harmonisation of the dissemination of information on the available evidence related to medicines use in pregnancy and during breastfeeding.

The 5.3 sub-task aim is to engage HCPs, pregnant and breastfeeding women and general public to stimulate pregnancy reporting through PV systems, by increasing their awareness that they can play an active role in increasing general knowledge about the safety of drug use during pregnancy and breastfeeding.

The objective of this report is to summarize communication actions performed in WP5 to disseminate knowledge about medicines use during pregnancy and lactation and to engage pregnant and breastfeeding women and healthcare professionals (HCPs) in the ConcePTION ecosystem between January and December 2022. The communications actions may have different targets and different messages.

For this report on the fourth year of the project, the main communication activities were related to engage key stakeholders in the ConcePTION ecosystem and to stimulate reporting on medicine use during pregnancy and breastfeeding.

Methods

The objective of the report is to make an inventory of communication actions performed in WP5 on the fourth year of the project.

The communication actions are classified by their objective:

- Engagement of pregnant and breastfeeding women and healthcare professionals in the ConcePTION ecosystem
- Increase awareness and stimulate reporting on medicine use in pregnancy and breastfeeding.

The communications actions are grouped by objective and are described using the following parameters: the geographical reach, the target audience, the channel used, the date of dissemination, and the main presenter.

Results

The communication actions for this report are divided into:

- Targeted actions to engage women in the ConcePTION ecosystem with focus on breastfeeding women to participate to breast milk collection
- Targeted actions to increase awareness and stimulate reporting via different channels

The ConcePTION project channels include a project website (<https://www.imi-conception.eu/>), a Twitter account, a YouTube channel, a LinkedIn account, and an e-mail newsletter. On Twitter (<https://twitter.com/IMIConcePTION>), we are followed by 511 users (as of 6 March 2023), with organic reach through their networks. During 2022, on average, our tweets averaged 7 300+ views per month. The project's newsletter audience is building through project events, and currently reaches 600+ subscribers, representing a wide variety of stakeholders. Through forwards, we are also reaching the

subscribers' networks. On average, newsletters reach 400 non-subscribers, with a high level of engagement (measured by clicks on links). On LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/imi-conception/>), the project has 336 followers, with a wide organic reach, where posts average 2 300+ views per month. YouTube (<https://www.youtube.com/@imiconception6542>) is primarily used as a video repository, and with only 28 subscribers, we have registered close to 3 000 views in total since the launch in February 2020.

Actions to engage women in the ConcePTION ecosystem were conducted through web communication and use of social media in various European countries and reaching international organizations. The communications actions to engage women have been conducted ConcePTION communication task force through different channels (twitter campaigns (<https://twitter.com/IMIConcePTION>), LinkedIn campaigns (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/imi-conception>), web posts (https://www.imi-conception.eu/news-details/?news_id=816), workshop and webinars, etc).

Table 1: Communication actions to engage women

Country/Region	Target Audience (Government, General Public, Women, Pregnant Women, HCP Organizations, Industry, Pharmacists, etc.)	Channel (Social Media, Newspaper, face to face, etc.)	Date	Who Presented
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (post in LinkedIn on women's views on learning health care system)	April 2022	IMIConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (post in LinkedIn on women's views on learning health care system)	April 2022	IHI
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (post in LinkedIn on breast milk collection webinar)	April 2022	IMIConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Webinar on European breast milk collection	May 2022	WP4 and BBMRI-ERIC
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Web (post in ConcePTION news on presentation of learning health care system)	May 2022	IMIConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Face to face presentation of ConcePTION mission at MPRINT hub meeting	June 2022	Myriam Sturkenboom
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Web (post in ConcePTION news on call for breastfeeding data)	August 2022	IMIConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Web (post in ConcePTION news on webinar recorded presentations)	August 2022	IMIConcePTION

The communications actions to raise awareness on the knowledge bank and to stimulate reporting have been conducted by task 5.3 members with support of ConcePTION communication task force through different channels (twitter campaigns (<https://twitter.com/IMIconcePTION>), LinkedIn campaigns (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/imi-conception>), web posts (https://www.imi-conception.eu/news-details/?news_id=816), workshop, and face to face presentations, etc).

Table 2: Communication actions to increase awareness on knowledge bank and to stimulate reporting of exposure during pregnancy and breastfeeding

Country/Region	Target Audience (Government, General Public, Women, Pregnant Women, HCP Organizations, Industry, Pharmacists, etc.)	Channel (Social Media, Newspaper, face to face, etc.)	Date	Who Presented
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (post in LinkedIn on workshop on pharmacovigilance in pregnancy)	March 2022	IMIconcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Web (post in ConcePTION news on workshop on pharmacovigilance in pregnancy)	March 2022	IMIconcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (post in LinkedIn on reporting medicine use)	March 2022	IMIconcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Web (post in ConcePTION news on reporting medicine use)	March 2022	IMIconcePTION
Global	ENTIS members	Face to face presentation at ENTIS annual meeting	September 2022	Ulrika Nörby and Brian Cleary on behalf of Task 5.2, 5.3 and 5.4
Global	ENTIS members	Poster presentation on knowledge bank standard operating procedure at ENTIS annual meeting	September 2022	Alison Oliver on behalf of Task 5.2
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (Post in LinkedIn on knowledge bank presentation at ENTIS annual)	September 2022	Ulrika Nörby
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (post in Twitter on medsafetyweek)	November 2022	IMIconcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (post in LinkedIn on medsafetyweek)	November 2022	IMIconcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Web (post in ConcePTION news on medsafetyweek)	November 2022	IMIconcePTION

Discussion and Conclusion

In the fourth year of the project, the communication efforts were focused on engaging women, raising awareness on medicines use during pregnancy and breastfeeding and stimulating reporting.